

**THE ROLE OF CLUSTERS IN THE EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF
PILGRIMAGE TOURISM SERVICE IN UZBEKISTAN**

Rakhimov Olim Khamidovich

Doctor of Philosophy in Economic Sciences, BSU

Yusupova Nigina Dzhurayevna

First year graduate student of the faculty of Economics, BSU

Abstract:

This article elucidates the role of clustering system and the ways of effective organization of it in tourism in Uzbekistan. The examples shown in the article are scientifically substantiated.

Keywords: *tourism, cluster, trained guides, local and foreign tourists, international relations, service.*

I. Introduction

Tourism has a great influence on the main sectors of the economy, such as transport, communication, construction, agriculture, that is, it acts as a kind of catalyst for socio-economic development of the country. The importance of tourism as a source of currency receipts and expansion of international relations is steadily increasing. Therefore, today we should pay special attention to improving the quality of services and keeping prices in common in the effective organization of Tourism. Tourism is a great contribution not only to cultural recreation, but also to the world recognition of the history, traditions and cultural heritage of one or another nation. Uzbekistan is also a tourist state frequented by tourists, and it is world famous for its rich history and historical steps. Most tourists visit our country to get a closer look at these historic sites and learn more about them. Several tourist zones have been established in Uzbekistan, one of which is the Bukhara region.

II. Discussion

In Uzbekistan, much attention is now paid to pilgrimage tourism. I think more attention should be paid to increasing not only foreign tourists, but also the number of local pilgrims in pilgrimage tourism. Visitors who are disillusioned with the pilgrimage may also encourage others to attend the pilgrimage. To do this, it is necessary to use the tourism cluster in the organization of the tourism sector as a whole and not individual pilgrimage tourism in our country. What is it? It is the case that each type of service is organized as a separate integrated system, which operates in cooperation with each other as an integrated network. Like the structure below:

For example, if hotels operate as a separate network, transport service itself as a separate network, guiding agencies are established and they themselves act as a separate network, which in turn leads to the formation of a natural competitive environment among service entities of the same type within each network. In a system where there is healthy competition, in turn, the quality of services improves, and prices decrease. This is how the functioning of the individual sectors involved in this process as a holistic tourism system is called a tourism cluster.

However, we have different problems with the organization of each network.

If we take the transport system, for example, the cost of aircraft or trains can be relatively cheap but the transports to the places to be visited will either be specially organized in the hotel structure only for those who use the hotel service, or you will get yourself in a private car either using the service of citizens who have a bus or a route.

To solve this problem, if a separate transport agency is created that provides such services, it will be a much more effective and meaningful pilgrimage if transports with modern amenities provide a service to local or foreign tourists accompanied by specially trained guides, since in cars with different amenities, visitors will not quickly get tired as well as specially trained guides in relation to ordinary as well as the creation of a travel map in each transport and brochures about the catering sectors that exist in these places, as well as hotels, this will lead to the functioning of tourism sectors as chains.

III. Conclusion

In conclusion, the organization of quality and affordable services in such networks, as described above, requires a large investment. Moreover, in order to attract investors, reliable and carefully prepared projects are needed, since usually investors invest in areas where the risk is low, fast and with a lot of profit.

REFERENCE:

1. Alexandrova, A. Yu. (2007). Tourism clusters: content, boundaries, mechanism of functioning. Modern problems of service and tourism, No1, pp. 51-61.
2. Moiseev, A. (2020). Benchmarking essence, stages and tools. (Accessed: 03.20.2020). Retrieved from <http://umom.biz/benchmarkingsushhnost-etapy-instrument/#ixzz6I9oSRU8L>
3. Demyanova, O.V., Runova, E.V., Vdovina, S.D., & Sadykova, D.R. (2016). Theoretical and methodological aspects of the formation of value added. PSE (Questions of economic theory. Macroeconomics). No. 4 (60), pp.72-76. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/>

teoretikometodologicheskie-aspekty-formirovaniyadobavlennoy-stoimosti
(дата обращения: 15.01.2020).

4. (2002). Financial credit encyclopedic dictionary. In Gryaznova A.G. (Ed.). Moscow: "Finance and statistics"

5. Ulyanchenko, L.A. (2012). Theory and methodology of the implementation of the cluster approach in the tourism industry (for example, the Moscow region). Abstract of diss ... Doctor of Economics St. Petersburg. S. 50.

6. Shoimardonkulovich, Y. D., & Hamidovich, R. O. (2020). Elaboration of regional strategies for the development and improvement of land and water in agriculture. *Academy*, (2 (53)), 16-17.

7. Shoimardonkulovich, Y. D., & Hamidovich, R. O. (2021). Pilgrimage tourism and its prospects in Uzbekistan. *Economics*, (1 (48)), 29-31.

8. Абдуллоев, А. Ж., Таирова, М. М., & Усманова, А. Б. (2020). Малый бизнес в сельском туризме и агротуризме. *Достижения науки и образования*, (5 (59)), 29-30.

9. Rahimov, O., Abdughaniyev, A., Oripov, M., Neira, X. X., Álvarez, J. C., & Cuesta, T. S. (2010). Considerations on water resources management in Central Asia. *Spanish journal of rural development*, 1(2), 51-59.

10. Giyazova, N. B., Bakayeva, M. A., & Giyazov, B. B. (2022). Public Financial Control Policy And Its Theoretical Foundations. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 128-130.

11. УСМАНОВА, А. (2021). Tourist Potential Of The Bukhara Region. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 6(6).

12. Rakhmatullaeva, F. M., & Aminova, N. B. (2022). Methodological Approaches to the Development of Ecological Tourism Logistics. *European journal of innovation in nonformal education*, 2(1), 207-211.

13. Agzamov, A. T., Rakhmatullaeva, F. M., & Giyazova, N. B. (2021, June). Marketing strategy for the competitiveness of modern enterprises. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 1-3).

14. Narzullayeva, G. S., & Bakayeva, M. A. (2022). Creative Management: Creative Opportunities In Business Process Management. *American Journal Of Social And Humanitarian Research*, 3(12), 58-63.

15. Navruz-zoda, Z. (2023). Development of Self-Employment of the Population as a Factor of Ensuring Economic Stability. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 33(33).

16. Niyozova, I. (2021). Approaches Aimed At Ensuring a High Quality of Education in the Training of Economists. *ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz)*, 8(8).

17. Nutfilloyevna, A. H. (2022). The Main Factors Of Economic Development Of The Tourism Industry. *European Multidisciplinary Journal Of Modern Science*, 4, 627-631.

18. Abdullayeva, H. (2021). The Effect Of Coronavirus Pandemic To Uzbekistan Tourism. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 7(7).

19. Rakhmatullaeva, F. M., & Aminova, N. B. (2022). Methodological Approaches to the Development of Ecological Tourism Logistics. *European journal of innovation in nonformal education*, 2(1), 207-211.

20. Dustova, A. (2022). Stimulating The Economic Growth Of Territories Through The Development Of Regional Tourism. *Центр Научных Публикаций (Buxdu. Uz)*, 12(12).

